

MRI-ESM3.4: Description of the Meteorological Research Institute Earth System Model Version 3.4

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Abstract

A new version of the Meteorological Research Institute Earth System Model, MRI-ESM3.4, has been developed for the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 7 (CMIP7). This document outlines its formulation, focusing on changes from its predecessor, MRI-ESM2.0, which was used in CMIP6.

MRI-ESM3.4 consists of four major component models coupled through the Scup coupler: an atmospheric general circulation model (MRI-AGCM4.4) incorporating land surface processes and terrestrial biogeochemical processes, an ocean–sea-ice general circulation model (MRI.COM version 5) with ocean biogeochemical processes, an aerosol model (MASINGAR mk-3r2), and an atmospheric chemistry model (MRI-CCM3.2).

Major updates from MRI-ESM2.0 include: (1) wide-ranging improvements to the physical, chemical, and biogeochemical processes across the component models, with some processes refined and others newly developed; and (2) substantial improvements in computational efficiency achieved through an updated atmospheric dynamical framework and the extension of a common grid system and parallelization approach to the aerosol and atmospheric chemistry component models.

Keywords

MRI-ESM3.4, CMIP7, Meteorological Research Institute, Earth system model, Atmospheric general circulation model, Ocean general circulation model, Aerosol model, Atmospheric chemistry model, Carbon cycle

1. Overview of MRI-ESM3.4

MRI-ESM3.4 consists of four major component models: an atmospheric general circulation model (Section 2) with land surface processes (Section 3) and terrestrial biogeochemical processes (Section 5.1), an ocean–sea-ice general circulation model (Section 4) with ocean biogeochemical processes (Section 5.2), an aerosol model (Section 6), and an atmospheric chemistry model (Section 7). These major component models are coupled through the Scup coupler (Yoshimura and Yukimoto, 2008), following primarily the same coupling approach as MRI-ESM2.0. MRI-ESM3.4 is an updated version of MRI-ESM2.0 (Yukimoto et al., 2019) with the same basic configuration. In the following sections, we outline the formulations of these component models, with a focus on modifications from MRI-ESM2.0. A comprehensive model description paper for MRI-ESM3.4 is currently in preparation for submission to a peer-reviewed journal.

2. Atmosphere

The atmospheric component of MRI-ESM3.4 is the MRI Atmospheric General Circulation Model version 4.4 (MRI-AGCM4.4), an updated version of MRI-AGCM3.5 (Yukimoto et al., 2011). MRI-AGCM4.4 is a global spectral atmospheric model that uses a semi-implicit semi-Lagrangian scheme. The model employs a sigma-pressure hybrid vertical coordinate system. The model can be configured across a wide range of horizontal resolutions. The model resolution for the CMIP7 experiments is TL159L100, corresponding to approximately 120 km horizontally and 100 vertical levels, compared with 80 vertical levels in CMIP6.

In MRI-AGCM4.4, the dynamical framework has been updated based on the Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA) Global Spectral Model version 1705 (GSM1705; Japan Meteorological Agency, 2019), which adopts reduced Gaussian grids, OpenMP parallelization, and a two-dimensional domain decomposition method for MPI parallelization to significantly improve computational efficiency. In addition, the two-dimensional domain decomposition method has been further improved to reduce MPI communication associated with semi-Lagrangian calculations. A double Fourier series option and a nonhydrostatic option have also been introduced for high-resolution simulations (Yoshimura and Matsumura, 2005; Yoshimura, 2012; Yoshimura, 2022; Yoshimura, 2026).

Many of the physical schemes in MRI-AGCM4.4 are derived from those of MRI-AGCM3.5. Some schemes are based on GSM1705 and its later versions, while others have been newly developed for MRI-AGCM4.4.

Several cloud macro- and microphysical processes have been improved over those in MRI-AGCM3.5. A physically based cloud-edge erosion scheme (Fielding et al., 2020) has been implemented to represent faster evaporation of convective clouds than that of stratiform clouds (Kawai et al., submitted). A prognostic cloud "origin attribute" has also been introduced to distinguish convective clouds from large-scale condensation clouds (Yukimoto and Kawai, submitted). The saturation adjustment treatment has been modified (Kawai et al., submitted). A smaller effective radius of cloud droplets and a smaller mass of ice crystals detrained from convection are prescribed over land than over ocean because aerosol concentrations are generally higher over land.

The cumulus convection scheme has been improved over the scheme used in MRI-AGCM3.5 (Yoshimura et al., 2015; Yukimoto et al., 2019). The scheme has been modified to account for subgrid-scale inhomogeneity in near-surface temperature and water vapor when determining the air parcels that initiate cumulus convection. The representation of rain–snow partitioning in the atmosphere has been refined using wet-bulb temperature. The resulting rain and snow near the surface are passed directly to the land and ocean models to improve precipitation-related energy conservation.

A new boundary layer scheme has been introduced based on the Eddy-Diffusivity/Mass-Flux (EDMF) parameterization (Siebesma et al., 2007; Olson et al., 2019; Shindo and Yoshimura, submitted). The scheme includes both local mixing based on the Mellor-Yamada-Nakanishi-Niino Level 2 scheme (Mellor and Yamada, 1982; Nakanishi and Niino, 2009) and nonlocal mixing by mass flux.

The longwave radiation scheme has been updated from the band-emissivity method based on Chou et al. (2001) (Japan Meteorological Agency, 2013) used in MRI-AGCM3.5 to a two-stream absorption approximation based on Li and Fu (2000) and Li (2002) (Yabu, 2013; Japan Meteorological Agency, 2019). This update has significantly accelerated the calculations and has enabled hourly, instead of three-hourly, longwave radiation calculations. Improvements have also been made in the treatment of surface emissivity, cloud optical properties (Dobbie et al., 1999; Lindner and Li, 2000), and overlap assumptions.

Subgrid orographic drag schemes (including turbulent orographic form drag, low-level blocked flow drag, and orographic gravity wave drag) and a non-orographic gravity wave drag scheme are implemented in MRI-AGCM4.4. These schemes are derived from JMA GSM (Japan Meteorological Agency, 2024), except for the total launch momentum flux in the non-orographic gravity wave parameterization, which depends on precipitation (Bushell et al., 2015) and jets and fronts (de la Cámara and Lott, 2015; Ribstein et al., 2022).

The skin SST scheme has been revised from the version used in MRI-AGCM3.5. In the present scheme, the cool-skin and warm-layer effects are estimated following Fairall et al. (1996) and Zeng and Beljaars (2005), respectively. The warm-layer treatment has been improved to allow temporal changes in the vertical temperature profile, as in the scheme used in JMA/MRI-CPS3 (Hirahara et al., 2023).

3. Land Surface

3.1 Land Surface Physics

In MRI-AGCM4.4 and MRI-ESM3.4, the land surface model has been updated from HAL (the name is formed from the first letters of Hydrology, Atmosphere, and Landsurface; Yukimoto et al., 2011), which was used in MRI-AGCM3.5 and MRI-ESM2.0, to a model based on the improved Simple Biosphere Model (iSiB) used in the JMA GSM.

As with HAL, iSiB represents vegetation, snow, and soil processes in detail. Snow and soil are represented using multilayer structures, with up to four snow layers and seven fixed soil layers, respectively. Compared with HAL, however, iSiB incorporates more recent findings, including those of Oleson et al. (2010), Best et al. (2011), and ECMWF (2015). In addition, the underlying land surface type classification has been changed from ISLSCP1 (Sellers et al., 1996) to GLC2000 (Bartholomé and Belward, 2005), which is based on more recent observational data.

One of the major modifications relative to the JMA version of iSiB is the introduction of a tiled representation of subgrid land surface types. Instead of each grid cell being represented by a single land surface type, multiple land surface types are represented individually within each grid cell. The water and heat budgets are calculated for each land surface type and are then area-averaged.

To ensure the consistency required for climate simulations, the conservation of the water budget was verified. The treatment of vegetation cover fraction has also been revised so that it is treated as a parameter dependent on land surface type, allowing its application to periods outside the satellite observation era. In addition, a snow albedo scheme based on the Snow Metamorphism and Albedo Process (SMAP) model (Niwano et al., 2012, 2021) has been introduced to account for the effects of aerosol deposition on the snow surface and the resultant changes in snow surface radiative properties.

3.2 Lake, River and Glacier

MRI-ESM3.4 incorporates GRiveT2, an updated river and lake model, and a simple glacier model, SMIST, both inherited from MRI-CGCM3 (Yukimoto et al., 2012).

GRiveT2 represents river transport using the $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ TRIP river routing dataset (Oki and Sud, 1998) and prognostically calculates river and lake water storage and temperature. SMIST converts excess snow accumulation over ice sheets (above 10 m water equivalent) into runoff, which is transported through river channels and discharged into the ocean as icebergs. Compared with MRI-ESM2.0 (Yukimoto et al., 2019), the representation of large lakes has been improved. Lake water storage, lake water temperature, and lake surface temperature are calculated from water and heat budgets, and a redistribution scheme has been introduced for the world's 17 largest lakes to maintain uniform water levels and physically consistent temperature distributions across multiple grid cells.

4. Ocean and Sea Ice

The ocean and sea-ice components of MRI-ESM3.4 use an ocean general circulation model developed at the Meteorological Research Institute (MRI) and named the MRI Community Ocean Model (MRI.COM) version 5 (Sakamoto et al., 2023). Its ocean part solves the primitive equations under the Boussinesq approximation. This model is formulated in the generalized orthogonal coordinate system and vertical z^* coordinate system proposed by Adcroft and Campin (2004). The sea-ice part shares the horizontal coordinate system with the ocean part. This sea-ice model is primarily based on the model of Mellor and Kantha (1989) and incorporates some additional processes/schemes, such as categorization by thickness, ridging, and rheology, from the Los Alamos sea ice model (CICE) version 3.14 (Hunke and Lipscomb, 2006).

The grid system used in the ocean and sea-ice components of MRI-ESM3.4 is largely the same as that of MRI-ESM2.0 (Yukimoto et al., 2019). It adopts the tripolar grid coordinate of Murray (1996), and its horizontal resolution is nominally 1 degree in longitude and 0.5 degrees in latitude with refinement down to 0.3 degrees from 10°S to 10°N . The ocean part has 61 layers in the vertical, and one of those is used for the bottom boundary layer (BBL) parameterization of Nakano and Suginozawa (2002). The thickness increases from 2 m at the top to 700 m, and the thickness of the BBL is 50 m. The model topography is the same as that in MRI-ESM2.0 but includes some minor modifications. The number of sea-ice categories increases from 5 in MRI-ESM2.0 to 8 with their upper boundaries of 0.1, 0.3, 0.6, 1.4, 2.4, 3.6, 5.0, and 30 m, respectively.

Here, we introduce some major updates from MRI-ESM2.0 in the physical components of these ocean and sea-ice models. Our ocean model adopts a new time-stepping scheme, the leap-frog Adams-Moulton (LFAM3) method used in the Regional Ocean Modeling System (Shchepetkin and McWilliams, 2005, 2009). We adopt the piecewise parabolic method of Colella and Woodward (1984) with a flux limiter of Lin et al. (1994) for passive tracer advection. We adopt a new neutral diffusion scheme of Shao et al. (2020). We use the two-dimensional thickness diffusion coefficient of Griffies et al. (2005), but its dimensionless factor has been doubled to 0.14. The vertical distribution of this eddy-

induced transport is calculated by solving a boundary-value problem as proposed by Ferrari et al. (2010). The background vertical diffusion coefficient is given by a parameterization of tide-induced vertical mixing proposed by Kawasaki et al. (2021). Unstable stratification activates a mass-flux parameterization of Gülk et al. (2024). We adopt a parameterization of mixed layer eddies (MLE) of Fox-Kemper et al. (2011). The ocean model is forced by geothermal heat (Lucazeau, 2019). Following the formulation of Toyoda et al. (2024), our new sea-ice model takes into account variable sea-ice salinity, and we renew the snow-ice formation process. We adopt the grease ice scheme of Mackie et al. (2020).

5. Carbon Cycle

5.1 Land Carbon Cycle

The land carbon cycle component of MRI-ESM3.4 is the dynamic global vegetation–wildfire model MRI-LPJ-LCF version 1.0 (MRI-LPJ-LCF1.0). This model is a dynamic global vegetation model coupled with a process-based wildfire module, which has been developed based on the LPJ-LMfire model (Pfeiffer et al., 2013). The major changes from the original LPJ-LMfire model are summarized below.

First, the model is driven by daily climate forcing from the atmospheric component of MRI-ESM3.4, enabling simulations of vegetation dynamics and wildfire activity at daily timesteps. Land-atmosphere CO₂ fluxes are exchanged with the atmospheric component. The allocation and establishment of grass plant functional types (PFTs) are calculated daily, whereas the establishment of tree PFTs is evaluated annually at the end of each year.

Second, leaf phenology is calculated daily from past information such as temperature and day length using established formulations (Foley et al., 1996; White et al., 1997; Botta et al., 2000; Arora, 2002; Kim et al., 2015). The wildfire module has been modified to incorporate modern human-induced fire activity, following Pechony and Shindell (2009), whereas the original LPJ-LMfire model accounts for preindustrial human-induced fires.

Third, the model includes a simplified representation of land-use change by distinguishing natural vegetation and agricultural tiles. The agricultural tile is represented using the same two grass PFTs as in the natural vegetation tile, without explicitly simulating crop-specific processes. When changes in land-use fractions occur, corresponding amounts of carbon in vegetation, litter, and surface soil reservoirs are assumed to be released to the atmosphere.

5.2 Ocean Carbon Cycle

The ocean carbon cycle is represented by the cycling of dissolved inorganic and organic carbon. Gas exchange with the atmosphere and carbonate chemistry incorporating

alkalinity are treated following the OMIP-CMIP6 protocol (Orr et al., 2017). Exchanges between dissolved inorganic and organic carbon are simulated using a Nutrient–Phytoplankton–Zooplankton–Detritus (NPZD) marine ecosystem model based on Schmittner et al. (2008, 2009). Our NPZD model includes nitrate, phosphate, and iron as nutrients, along with single classes of phytoplankton, zooplankton, and detritus. It also simulates the cycling of oxygen and includes a vertically one-dimensional representation of the calcium carbonate cycle. Biological uptake and remineralization occur with fixed elemental ratios among constituents. A general performance evaluation is provided by Tsujino et al. (2026).

The major update from MRI-ESM2.0 is a revision of biological production rates. In MRI-ESM2.0, the limitation of biological production by micronutrients such as iron was implicitly represented by prescribing a globally low maximum biological production rate. In MRI-ESM3.4, this treatment has been revised by increasing the maximum biological production rate and explicitly introducing iron limitation based on dissolved iron concentrations. The revision is achieved by adding two new tracers, dissolved and particulate iron, to represent iron cycling in the model. The iron cycle has been implemented by following the formulation presented by Shigemitsu et al. (2012) with scavenging modified according to Moore and Braucher (2008). As a result, the seasonal variation of surface CO₂ flux in the subpolar North Pacific is improved, with CO₂ taken up by the ocean in summer and outgassed in winter, without degrading performance in other High-Nutrient–Low-Chlorophyll regions. The effectiveness of this change is demonstrated by Tsujino et al. (2026).

6. Aerosol

The aerosol component model used in MRI-ESM3.4 is the Model of Aerosol Species in the Global Atmosphere mark-3 revision 2 (MASINGAR mk-3r2), an updated version of MASINGAR mk-2r4-climate used in MRI-ESM2.0 (Yukimoto et al., 2019; Oshima et al., 2020). The aerosol model calculates the physical and chemical processes of atmospheric aerosols, such as emission, transport, diffusion, chemical reactions, and dry and wet deposition. The model treats non-sea-salt sulfate, black carbon, organic carbon, sea salt, mineral dust, and aerosol precursor gases. The size distributions of sea salt and mineral dust are divided into ten discrete bins, while the sizes of the other aerosols are represented by lognormal size distributions. The model is interactively coupled with the other component models in MRI-ESM3.4, enabling the representation of the effects of the gases and aerosols on the climate (e.g., the interactions of aerosols with radiation, clouds, and the surface albedo of snow and ice). The chemical species required for sulfur chemistry in the aerosol model are provided from MRI-CCM3.2 via the coupler. MRI-ESM3.4 includes the interactions of aerosols with ice clouds, the same as in MRI-ESM2.0.

The major updates to the new aerosol model (MASINGAR mk-3r2) compared to MRI-ESM2.0 are described briefly below. The vertical resolution has increased from 80 to 100 levels (the model top remains unchanged), while the horizontal resolution remains at TL95 (approximately 180 km). Similar to MRI-AGCM4.4 and MRI-CCM3.2, the new aerosol model has adopted the reduced Gaussian grid approach, OpenMP parallelization, and the modified two-dimensional domain decomposition method that reduces MPI communication associated with semi-Lagrangian calculations. These changes have largely enhanced the computational efficiency of the aerosol model. To be consistent with MRI-AGCM4.4, we have implemented the EDMF parameterization and modified the treatment of clouds in the aerosol model. We have modified the treatments of aerosols and their precursor emissions, as well as the wet scavenging of aerosols, in the aerosol model. The dust deposition flux is used in the biological production rate in the ocean carbon cycle via the coupler.

7. Atmospheric Chemistry

The atmospheric chemistry component of MRI-ESM3.4 is the MRI Chemistry Climate Model version 3.2 (MRI-CCM3.2), which simulates the distribution and temporal evolution of ozone and various trace gases from the troposphere to the middle atmosphere. It is an improved version of MRI-CCM2.1, which was used as the atmospheric chemistry component of MRI-ESM2.0 (Yukimoto et al., 2019), and is interactively coupled with MRI-AGCM4.4 and MASINGAR mk-3r2. The major updates in MRI-CCM3.2 are summarized as follows.

First, polar stratospheric chemistry processes have been improved. The PSC representation has been updated by introducing supercooled ternary solutions (STS; type 1b PSC) consisting of $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4\text{-HNO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ droplets, and by improving the formation and sedimentation processes of nitric acid trihydrate (NAT; type 1a PSC) and ice particles (type 2 PSC) (Carslaw et al., 1995; Grainger et al., 1995; Kirner et al., 2011; Luo et al., 1995). In addition, the number of heterogeneous reactions on PSCs has been increased from 6 to 10, incorporating key reactions involved in halogen activation (Hanson et al., 1996; Solomon, 1999; Hanson, 2003; Burkholder et al., 2020). Two gas-phase reactions relevant to chlorine activation have also been introduced following Burkholder et al. (2020).

Second, the reduced Gaussian grid approach, OpenMP parallelization, and the modified two-dimensional domain decomposition method that reduces MPI communication associated with semi-Lagrangian calculations have been implemented to significantly enhance the computational efficiency of the atmospheric chemistry model. These implementations are consistent with those used in MRI-AGCM4.4 and MASINGAR mk-3r2.

Third, the vertical resolution has been increased from 80 to 100 levels, adopting the same vertical structure as MRI-AGCM4.4. In contrast, the horizontal resolution is maintained at T42 spectral resolution (approximately 280 km), as in MRI-CCM2.1, a resolution that differs from that of MRI-AGCM4.4.

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